

Microstructure and high temperature mechanical properties of refractory Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr alloy prepared by laser directed energy deposition

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ABSTRACT

The microstructure and mechanical properties of Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr complex concentrated alloy (CCA) prepared from the blend of elemental powders by laser directed energy deposition (L-DED) technique were investigated. Variation of the laser power and laser-induced substrate platform preheating were utilized to deposit 3D bulk samples. Deposition at maximum laser power of 500 W followed by long-term homogenization heat treatment at 1200 °C results in the crack free, locally homogeneous material. The final chemical composition of the deposited sample Cr15-Nb28-Ti23-Zr34 differs from the equimolar composition of the blended elemental powders due to Cr evaporation during deposition. The homogenized microstructure is formed by equiaxed grains with the size below 100 μm and fine Cr₂(Zr, Nb, Ti) Laves phase particles dispersed predominantly at grain boundaries. Mechanical properties were investigated by compression tests at RT, 400 °C and 800 °C. At RT, the homogenized alloy exhibits yield stress of 1558 MPa (ductility is about 8 %). Deformation at 400 °C decreases the yield stress by 20 %, while the ductility remained unchanged. Serrated flow appearing at compression curves at 400 °C can be attributed to the PLC effect. It was shown that L-DED technique can produce refractory CCAs directly from elemental powders by careful optimization of processing parameters. Deposition with a thermally insulating platform effectively suppresses crack formation and reduces the number of unmelted Nb particles. However, the utilization of the homogenization heat treatment after the deposition is required to achieve microstructural homogeneity at the length-scale of powder particles (tens of micrometers).

1. Introduction

Refractory complex concentrated alloys (RCCAs) have been originally developed for high temperature applications [1,2] due to high melting temperature of constituents and a possible sluggish diffusion effect [3]. In a wide range of compositions, these alloys have a single-phase body-centered cubic structure (bcc) which allows achieving both high strength and good ductility [4,5]. In the last decade, the biomedical applications of bcc CCAs have emerged as a growing area of interest [6,7]. Most refractory metals are considered biocompatible [8]. The TiNbTaZrMo alloy with bcc structure exhibits even better biocompatibility than commercially pure Ti [9]. Refractory metal CCAs based on Nb, Ta, Ti, Zr elements expand the concept of modern Ti alloys and are promising metallic biomaterials for the replacement of hard tissues in artificial hip joints or dental implants because of their excellent

specific strength and corrosion resistance [10]. Most studies of the Nb-Ta-Ti-Zr system were performed either in equimolar NbTaTiZr [11, 12] or in Ti-rich compositions [10,13]. However, the preparation of the complex concentrated alloys (CCAs) combining high melting point elements (W, V, Nb, Mo, Ta, Ti, Zr) with elements with lower melting point and/or high vapor pressure, such as Cr or Al is difficult by conventional arc melting, where the material must be remelted several times to attain reasonable homogeneity [9].

Additive manufacturing (AM) of metallic materials has many advantages over traditional production methods. With the capabilities of producing near-net shape parts, it cuts down excess material and machining needs, reducing overall manufacturing costs. Additionally, AM can produce complex geometries that would be difficult to manufacture conventionally. Finally, AM is capable of rapid prototyping when compared to arc melting.

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Laser-directed energy deposition (L-DED), as one of the workhorses of additive manufacturing (AM) techniques, has already been successfully used for the deposition of CCAs [14,15]. High-energy laser beam is used for melting the metal powder, which is fed from a single or multiple computer-controlled hoppers directly into the laser beam. Using elemental powders instead of pre-alloyed powder is beneficial in terms of initial costs and, more importantly, absolute variability of chemical composition. On the other hand, it is more demanding for optimization of deposition parameters. The parameters of deposition (laser power, scanning speed) need to be adjusted repetitively for each alloying composition to prepare a fully dense and homogenous material [16,17].

On the contrary, the studies on CCAs containing refractory metals prepared by laser melting are scarce. CrFeNiTiZr alloy was successfully prepared by laser melting and comprised mainly hexagonal Laves phase [18]. However, increasing laser power and additional remelting by laser stabilized the bcc phase solid solution [19]. In the review by Torralba dedicated to CCAs prepared by powder metallurgy [20] it is claimed that until then only a single study on true refractory metal CCAs prepared by AM was reported [21]. In their study authors aim for preparing MoNbTaW CCA from mixed elemental powders and the mixture was delivered to the melt pool from a single container. It is stressed that the purity of inert atmosphere and the processing parameters are crucial for achieving intended equimolar composition and material ductility. In the follow-up study, the authors successfully prepared equimolar HfNbTaTiZr alloy with a single-phase bcc structure and high hardness [22].

The influence of the Cr content on the microstructure and mechanical properties of ZrNbTaHf_{0.2}Cr_x refractory high entropy alloys prepared by arc melting was investigated by Fang [23]. Gradual increase in the microhardness and the yield stress was observed with increasing Cr concentration, due to the more pronounced Laves phase precipitation. Similarly, increasing values of microhardness and yield stress were observed in bcc Ti-Nb-Zr-Cr alloys with increasing Cr concentration and were attributed to the enhanced solid-solution strengthening [24].

The main objective of the current study was to develop the procedure for additive manufacturing of Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr alloys from a mixture of elemental powders by the L-DED technique. Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr is a representative system of the group of RCCAs. Variation of the laser power and laser-induced substrate plate heating were utilized to deposit 3D bulk samples with the homogeneity at the length-scale of powder particles. In addition to the thorough microstructure characterisation, mechanical properties of the homogenized samples were investigated in compression at room and elevated temperatures.

2. Materials and methods

Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr complex concentrated alloy (CCA) was deposited from the equimolar mixture of the elemental powders using commercially available apparatus Insstek MX-Lab equipped with Ytterbium fibre laser source of the maximum power of 500 W. The device allows printing in the manual mode (printing with constant power) or in the automatic Direct Metal Tooling (DMT) mode, which changing the laser power to maintain the constant layer height, using two visible-light cameras for monitoring the distance of the melt pool from the nozzle, which is useful mainly for deposition of pre-alloyed powders. DMT parameters are pre-optimized for manufacturing of various common materials, but none of them was found to be suitable for deposition of the Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr CCA as the microstructure of deposited samples contained numerous unmelted Nb particles, significant porosity and furthermore, a large variation of layer height occurred.

Consequently, the constant power regime with the laser power of 300 W, 400 W and 500 W was utilized to find the optimal printing parameters for the deposition of the Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr samples. The temperature of the platform was monitored by thermocouples welded to the bottom side of the substrate plate (Ti Grade 2, thickness 5 mm). Each sample deposition was performed directly above the position one of the thermocouples so that, the platform temperature evolution at different laser

powers was measured accurately. Importantly, the substrate plate was thermally insulated from the underlaid platform by the ceramic fibre insulating plate Ultraboard 1850–400 (80 % Al₂O₃ + 20 % SiO₂) by Schupp (Aachen, Germany) with specified thermal conductivity of 0.34 W/mK. The substrate plate had a thickness of 40 mm. In addition, deposition onto a conventional conductive platform was also performed with a maximum laser power of 500 W, to compare the platform temperatures reached during deposition. The experimental setup with thermally insulated platform is shown in Fig. 1a. Deposition with thermally insulated platform resulted in an elevated temperature of the platform, heated by the residual deposition heat, without any additional heat source, as shown in Fig. 2a. The temperature of the substrate plate during deposition was in the range of 300–500 °C, depending on the laser power. For greater heat accumulation, the so-called dwell time, i.e. the delay between the contour and filling deposition was turned off. The comparison of the temperature attained during deposition by 500 W onto a conventional thermally conductive build plate relatively to the thermally insulated plate is apparent from Fig. 2b. The direct contact of the plate with the bottom part of 3D printer was checked by thermocouples welded in the top part of the non-insulated platform, at the distance less than 1 cm from the deposited samples. Temperature of only 300 °C was attained during deposition on the conductive platform at the laser power of 500 W.

Solid blocks having the square shape base of 10 × 10 mm² and the final height of 7–10 mm, depending on the laser power, were produced, cf. Fig. 1b. Nominal layer height of 150 μm, ZigZag link CF/CFC printing strategy (rotation by 90° between the successive layers), print speed of 850 mm/min and a hatch distance of 300 μm were used for samples deposition. Given the laser beam diameter of 400 μm, these printing conditions yield the 100 μm overlay of the adjacent runs. The designation "Zig-Zag link CF/CFC" means that during the deposition, the contour (C) of the layer is deposited first, followed by the filling (F) using the ZigZag scans [25]. Similarly, in the next layer, additional contour is deposited after the filling, without switching-off of the laser at any point during the deposition.

Commercially available powders of Ti Grade 2, Nb, Zr, and Cr were used in this study. The chemical composition and the particle size distribution of the powders are listed in Table 1. The backscatter SEM image of the pre-mixed elemental powders and the corresponding EDS map are shown in Fig. 3, indicating the spherical shape of powder particles. Equimolar mixture of the powders was used for the preparation of the samples. Before the deposition, the equimolar mixture of the powders was mixed 3 times for 1 hour in a laboratory mechanical mixer. The powder flow is controlled by a vibration system, which enables the variation of the mass flow from 0.05 g/min to 20 g/min. The mass flow of 0.5 g/min was used for the deposition at all power values. The deposition was performed in the argon protective atmosphere with purity 99.9999 %. The argon flow was automatically controlled during the deposition, to keep the oxygen content well below 100 ppm. The oxygen content was monitored using a built-in sensor based on an electrochemical cell. Typical oxygen content in the chamber after the deposition was around 45 ppm and was held for 2 hours after the end of the deposition to prevent the contamination by oxygen and nitrogen during the sample cooling. Furthermore, the area of the melt pool was locally shielded by Ar flowing from the deposition head with the flow of 8 l/min. The gas flow transporting the powder to the melt pool was set to 3 l/min.

To assess the efficiency of subsequent homogenization treatment, selected samples parts were annealed at 1200 °C/180 h in 99.9999 % Ar atmosphere (in a vertical tube furnace Nabertherm RHTV 120–600/18) and water quenched. Each sample in as-deposited condition was cut along the building direction into two identical halves. The plane of this central cut (i.e. the xz plane, as shown in Fig. 1c) was used for the investigation. First, microhardness was measured along four lines (see Fig. 1c). The distance between individual indents along the line was set to 250 μm. Microhardness indents helped to trace the positions of

Fig. 1. (a) The experimental setup used for the sample deposition at elevated temperatures. (b) examples of the deposited samples and (c) the schematic image of the deposited sample (half-cube) showing the positions of the performed experiments.

Fig. 2. Platform temperature evolution during the sample deposition (a) at different laser powers with the thermally insulated substrate plate and (b) at the laser power of 500 W with and without insulated substrate.

Table 1

The size and the chemical composition of powders used for 3D printing.

Powder	Ti grade 2	Cr (99.9 %)	Nb (99.9 %)	Zr (99.9 %)
Suppliers	(AP&C, Canada)	(Stanford Adv. Materials, USA)	(CAMEX, Czech Republic)	
Particle size	45–150 μm	50–150 μm		
Content of elements in wt%				
O	0.17	0.02	0.15	0.22
N	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.03

subsequent experiments (SEM, EDS, XRD). SEM images were taken in the vicinity of each indent along the lines 1 and 2, EDS line profile was measured along the line 2. After these measurements, the part of the deposited sample containing lines 1 and 2 was homogenization treated to allow the comparison of microstructure changes in the same places along the lines 1 and 2 in the as-deposited and homogenized sample (cf. Fig. 1c). After the homogenization treatment, the sample was reground and repolished (see below) and a new set of HV, SEM, EDS measurements was performed. Finally, X-ray diffraction was performed on homogenized material at three positions along the line 2. The spot with the diameter of 0.3 mm, 2D curved detector and in-place camera for the precise selection of the investigated area on the sample surface were employed together with rocking the sample in φ and χ axes for better statistics.

The sample preparation consisted of the mechanical grinding of the xz -samples plane (see Fig. 1c) using SiC papers with decreasing grit size down to the 5 μm , followed by fine polishing by 20 % solution of hydrogen peroxide in OP-S colloidal silica suspension for 7 min. The samples for transmission XRD were ground to the thickness of about 300 μm by 1200-grit SiC paper. Microhardness measurements were performed under the applied load of 500 g and a dwell time of 10 s, employing automatic microhardness tester Qness Q10A. SEM FEI Quanta 200 and Apreo 2 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) electron microscopes equipped with EDAX EDS detectors and the diffractometer Rigaku Rapid II with a sealed Mo tube, MoK α graphite monochromator, and curved 2D detector for measurements in the transmission mode were used. Oxygen content in the as-deposited and homogenized samples was measured by carrier gas hot extraction (Bruker G8 GALILEO analyser). Mechanical properties at RT, 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ were investigated in compression with an initial strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} using a Zwick Roell Z250 machine with a maximum load cell capacity of 250 kN. The samples tested at the elevated temperature were stabilized for 10 minutes at particular temperature before the test. The cylindrical samples (diameter 4 mm, height 6 mm) were prepared by the electrical discharge machining from the bottom part of the homogenized cubes. The compression direction was parallel to the building direction z . The strain measurement was performed using the contactless video extensometer, employing facet sizes of 50×100 pixels and an optical system

from Zwick Roell.

3. Experimental results

3.1. Microstructure of as-deposited samples using laser power of 300, 400 and 500 W

Microstructure observations of 3D printed samples (in the xz plane, cf. Fig. 1c) revealed the presence of undissolved or partly melted Nb particles (denoted by red arrows) in the as-deposited samples, see Fig. 4. The number of Nb particles decreases with increasing laser power, see Fig. 4a-c. The sample deposited by 500 W at the conductive platform contains significantly higher number of undissolved Nb particles as compared to samples deposited with thermally insulated platform. Furthermore, the sample deposited at 400 W, and particularly the ones deposited at 300 W (insulated platform) and at 500 W (conductive platform) contain numerous cracks. Based on these findings, only the sample deposited at 500 W with insulated platform was further analysed in detail.

3.2. Porosity and microhardness of the sample prepared by laser power of 500 W

Image analysis of the microstructure of the sample with insulated platform deposited at 500 W revealed the residual porosity of 0.68 %. The results of the microhardness measurement of the as-deposited sample along four lines (cf. Fig. 1c) are plotted in Fig. 5a. The microhardness gradually increases from about 440 HV in the bottom part to about 480 HV in the top part of the sample. The HV values determined along the line 1 are higher by about 30 HV and feature greater variance than the overall trend. Note that the area around the line 1 corresponds to the left part of sample, which contained higher number of undissolved Nb particles. The microhardness difference between line 1 and 2 diminished in the homogenized sample, cf. Fig. 5. As shown in Fig. 5b, the microhardness increases linearly with increasing sample height (building direction/ z -axis).

3.3. Microstructure and composition of as-deposited and homogenized conditions

The EDS lines profile corresponding to the area in the vicinity of the line 2 for the as-deposited and homogenized samples is plotted in the Fig. 6. EDS line profile was evaluated from the discrete rectangular EDS pattern consisting of perpendicular lines of the length of 266 μm determined with the step of 50 μm along the line 2. As it is apparent from Fig. 6a, the chemical composition of the as-deposited sample significantly deviates from the equiatomic composition. The concentration of Ti is consistent with the premixed equiatomic composition of powders. The content of the Zr and Nb varied around 30 at% whereas, Cr exhibited the biggest deviation from the equiatomic 25 % content. Its

Fig. 3. (a) Backscatter SEM image and (b) EDS map of the blend of elemental powders used for the sample deposition.

Fig. 4. Overview (low-magnification) light micrographs of the samples deposited on insulated platform by constant laser power of (a) 300 W, (b) 400 W and (c) 500 W, and (d) 500 W, deposited on the conductive platform.

Fig. 5. Microhardness evolution across the height of Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr samples (a) as-deposited sample and (b) subsequently homogenized sample. Error bars are plotted only for line 1 for the clarity.

concentration at the bottom part is only 15 at% and then, Cr concentration gradually increases with increasing height of the sample. After the homogenization treatment, strong oscillation of the Cr concentration around 15 at% is apparent along the sample height (see Fig. 6b) and is caused by precipitation of Cr-rich Laves phase particles as shown and discussed below.

Direct microstructure observations by SEM at different sample

heights (different z) of both as-deposited and homogenized conditions are summarised in Fig. 7. The as-deposited (D) sample exhibits a dendritic structure, the size of the dendrites decreases along the building direction (z -axis), see Fig. 7a-c. The microstructure of homogenized (H) specimens consists of predominantly equiaxed grains of the size below 100 μm , which are visible in Fig. 7d-f due to the channelling contrast. The presence of the dark particles of the secondary phase at the grain

Fig. 6. Chemical composition evolution along the z-axis of (a) as-deposited and (b) homogenization treated sample evaluated from EDS strip.

Fig. 7. Backscatter SEM images in the (a,d) bottom, (b,e) middle and (c,f) top part of the as-deposited (D) (a-c) and homogenized (H) sample (d-f).

boundaries is clearly seen. The oxygen content in both bottom and top part of as-deposited samples was found to be 0.36 wt%. After the long-term homogenization treatment, the oxygen content increases to about 0.60 wt%.

From the EDS map shown in Fig. 8a it is apparent, that the secondary phase (appearing dark in SEM images) is enriched by Cr. Detailed investigation by EDS showed that besides Cr, the phase contains also Ti, Nb and Zr, see Fig. 8b. The average chemical composition evaluated from EDS line profiles of 3 particles is Cr50-Zr21-Nb17-Ti12. Furthermore, the EDS mapping enables separation of the matrix and secondary particles as shown in Fig. 9. The area fraction of secondary particles differs in different places along the building direction: 11 % (bottom), 14 % (middle), 17 % (top) area of the sample, cf. Fig. 9. The chemical composition of the secondary particles evaluated from EDS phase maps (Cr49-Zr23-Nb16-Ti12) is constant irrespectively of the position within the sample (see Table 2) and is consistent with chemical composition evaluated from EDS lines. Moreover, the chemical composition of the matrix slightly differs along the building direction (see also Table 2). Nb

content in the matrix increases from the bottom to the top part at the expense of the Zr, while the content of Cr a Ti remains constant. The overall chemical composition of the homogenized material evaluated from EDS phase maps is listed also in Table 2 to stress the composition variations of individual elements along the building direction.

Fig. 10 shows the microstructure in the vicinity of unmelted Nb particle in as-deposited condition (Fig. 10a), in comparison with similar area within homogenized sample (Fig. 10b). In the as-deposited sample, the Nb particle is clearly identified, as confirmed by EDS (Fig. 10a) while upon homogenization treatment (Fig. 10b), the original Nb particle effectively dissolved and, indeed, left behind a homogenized chemical composition. On the other hand, the presence of the Nb particle after the deposition resulted in the absence of secondary phases in this area after homogenization.

3.4. XRD phase analysis

The phase composition in homogenized samples was investigated by

Fig. 8. (a) Cr EDS map and (b) EDS line profile measured across the secondary phase particles in homogenized sample.

Fig. 9. EDS phase maps from the (a) bottom, (c) middle and (d) top part of the sample obtained on the homogenized sample. Laves phase particles are in green.

Table 2

The overall chemical composition, chemical composition of the matrix and the secondary Laves phase in different regions of the homogenized sample (in at%).

Overall	Cr	Nb	Ti	Zr
Top	16	30	24	30
Middle	15	29	23	33
Bottom	13	28	25	34
Matrix	Cr	Nb	Ti	Zr
Top	8	3	27	31
Middle	8	33	26	33
Bottom	8	30	27	35
Laves phase	Cr	Nb	Ti	Zr
Top	49	16	12	23
Middle	49	15	12	24
Bottom	49	16	12	23

XRD at different places along the building direction (see Fig. 1c). The individual XRD patterns are shown in Fig. 11. In consistency with the direct microstructure observations by SEM, two phases were identified, namely the BCC phase corresponding to the matrix and the secondary Laves phase with the cubic C15 structure based on Cr_2Zr , but also containing dissolved Ti, Nb and Zr atoms. The lattice parameter therefore can differ from the model phase.

3.5. Compression tests of homogenized samples

The true stress-strain compression curves measured at RT and elevated temperatures are plotted in Fig. 12a. At RT and 400 °C the compression curves exhibit mild work hardening up to failure, in contrast to the samples deformed at 800 °C where steady state plastic

flow is apparent from the strain of about 12 %. Moreover, serrated flow can be observed on compression curves at 400 °C, see the inset in the upper right corner of Fig. 12a. The values of the yield stress, the compressive strength and the ductility evaluated from compression curves are plotted in Fig. 12b. The sample deformed at RT exhibits the yield stress of 1558 MPa, the compressive strength of 1827 MPa and the ductility of about 8 %. At the temperature of 400 °C the yield stress decreases by about 20 %, while the ductility remains constant. At 800 °C the yield stress decreased down to 331 MPa, while the sample was continuously deformed up to the strain of 50 %, when the test was interrupted.

4. Discussion

Successful deposition of refractory Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr CCAs from the elemental powders instead of pre-alloyed powder is more challenging in terms of the optimization of the deposition process and individual deposition parameters. In the present study, the influence of the laser power (300 W, 400 W and 500 W) on the microstructure homogeneity was investigated. The laser power was changed to control the energy density imposed to the melt pool. The energy density imposed to the melt pool at 300 W (469 J/mm^3), 400 W (626 J/mm^3) and 500 W (782 J/mm^3) was calculated as the value of laser power divided by the scanning speed, hatch spacing and layer thickness. Despite the deposition at the maximum laser power of 500 W, the microstructure of the sample printed on the conductive substrate contained numerous unmelted Nb particles, as shown in Fig. 4d. Deposition on the substrate platform placed on an insulating ceramic fiber plate helped to minimize the heat transfer to the underlaid machine massive platform that is permanently cooled and thus, allows to keep the high temperature of substrate during deposition. The deposition at the elevated temperature

Fig. 10. EDS line measured on (a) as-deposited and (b) homogenized sample in the area of the original unmelted and subsequently fully dissolved Nb particle, respectively.

Fig. 11. XRD patterns at different places along the building direction of homogenized samples. Patterns were shifted vertically for clarity.

was inspired by the results published in [17], where the platform pre-heating significantly reduced the number of undissolved Ta/Nb particles in the 3D printed Nb-Ta-Ti-Zr refractory alloy deposited also from the blend of elemental powders. The experimental setup employed in this study resulted in heating of the substrate platform during the deposition to the temperature ranging from 300 to 500 °C, depending on the laser power (cf. Fig. 2a) and consequent reduction of the fraction of

undissolved Nb particles, cf. Fig. 4c and d. Moreover, deposition on the insulated substrate reduces temperature gradients created at the edge of the meltpool which in turn decreases the strain concentrations and thus decreases the formation of the cracks during deposition. The cracking suppression was observed at the substrate temperature exceeding 400 °C. The FEM simulations of temperature and thermal stress fields in the vicinity of the meltpool for different values of energy densities were reported for V0.5Nb0.5ZrTi high entropy alloy prepared by selective laser melting (SLM) in [26]. During the deposition at 500 W, the oxygen content increases from 0.13 wt% (in premixed powders) to 0.36 wt% (in the as-deposited sample). Possible massive samples oxidation (e.g. by order of magnitude) was reduced by the protective Ar atmosphere inside the chamber of the 3D printer and by an additional Ar flow around the deposition spot. Despite the platform insulation and consequent heating, some unmelted Nb particles were still present in the samples deposited even by the maximum attainable laser power of 500 W.

Preparation of the Cr-Nb-Ti-Zr alloy from the equimolar mixture of the elemental powders resulted in the composition (Cr15-Nb28-Ti23-Zr34) that significantly varied from an equimolar blend of elemental powders used for the deposition. This difference can be attributed to a pronounced Cr evaporation in the premixed powders, as the boiling temperature of Cr (2672 °C) is just 200 K above the melting temperature of Nb (2477 °C). Moreover, partial powder separation could be also considered, as the feeders work on the vibrating principle, and the flowability of individual powders in the premixed compound is not identical. The evaporation is more pronounced at the bottom parts of the

Fig. 12. (a) Compression curves at RT and elevated temperature of 400 °C, 800 °C and (b) the values of the yield stress, the compressive strength and the ductility evaluated from the compression curves. Inset in the upper right corner of Fig. 12a shows magnified view on the serrated flow at the compression curves at 400 °C.

deposited samples, which is consistent with a numerical model describing the temperature evolution in individual layers during the L-DED process [27]. According to the reported numerical model, it is apparent, that the already built layers in the bottom part of the sample are repeatedly reheated by the deposition of the layers above. As a result, the already deposited layers remain at the elevated temperature for a longer time as compared to the layers built on top of them, which could accelerate the increased Cr evaporation in the bottom part of the sample. The above described chemical inhomogeneities resulted in the microstructure variation along the building direction (z-direction) in the homogenized specimen. Namely, the fraction of the Cr rich secondary Laves phase increases along the building direction (z-axis). The chemical composition of the secondary particles Cr₄₉Zr₂₃Nb₁₆Ti₁₂ (determined from EDS phase maps) was found to be constant in the whole sample volume. The secondary particles were identified by XRD measurements as Laves (C15) phase on the basis of Cr₂Zr phase. The secondary phases particles of the similar composition (Cr_{51.5}Zr_{20.6}Nb_{15.8}Ti_{12.1}) were observed in the equimolar CrNbTiZr alloy prepared by vacuum arc melting and hot isostatic pressing after the homogenization annealing at 1200 °C for 24 h [28]. The composition of secondary particles differed from the model binary Cr₂Zr type Laves C15 phase, containing 66.6 at% Cr and 33.4 at% Zr. Accordingly, the Laves phase in the homogenized sample can be referred to as Cr₂(Zr, Nb, Ti) type, while considering, that some Cr could be substituted by Zr, Nb or Ti atoms. Finally, according to the results shown in Fig. 10, it is apparent, that the Cr₂(Zr, Nb, Ti) type particles precipitate at the temperature of 1200 °C rapidly, before the Nb particles are dissolved. As a result, the areas of the original Nb particles are depleted of the secondary phase particles.

The amount of Zr in the matrix, which was almost constant along the as-deposited sample (Fig. 6a), gradually decreases from bottom towards the top part of the homogenized sample (Fig. 6b). On the other hand, the amount of the Cr dissolved in the matrix rapidly decreases to the value of about 8 at%. Hence, it seems that the fraction of the Cr-rich (and Zr-rich) Laves phase is given by the total Cr content, resulting in the stabilization of the Cr content in the matrix at around 8 %. The content of Zr in the matrix consequently adjusts according to the fraction of the Laves phase driven by the Cr content (see Table 2).

The 3D printed CrNbTiZr alloy contains a disordered BCC phase and an ordered Cr₂(Zr, Nb, Ti) type Laves phase. The increasing microhardness along the building direction is consistent with the increasing fraction of Cr₂(Zr, Nb, Ti) type Laves phases during the deposition. The Laves phase is stable at room temperature and completely dissolves above 1363 °C according to the modeled equilibrium diagrams of the equimolar CrNbTiZr alloy [28]. Such stability of the Laves phase pre-determines the designed alloys for high temperature applications. Consistently, the yield stress of the 3D printed CrNbTiZr alloy decreased only by 20 %, from 1558 MPa (RT) to 1237 MPa (400 °C), while the ductility remained constant (8 %). Lower values of the compression yield stress of 1260 MPa (RT) and 300 MPa (800 °C) were observed in the equiatomic CrNbTiZr alloy prepared by arc melting, at the initial strain rate of 10⁻³ s⁻¹ [29]. In addition, the equiatomic NbTiVZr alloy prepared by arc melting exhibits significantly lower compression yield stress of 1105 MPa and 187 MPa at RT and 800 °C, respectively. It can be attributed to the absence of the ordered Laves phase due to the absence of Cr [29]. On the other hand, V0.5Nb0.5ZrTi refractory high entropy alloy with BCC single phase structure fabricated by SLM using elemental powders exhibits compression yield stress of 1450 MPa and ductility around 20 % at RT [26]. Comparable compressive yield stress of 1635 MPa but significantly larger plasticity of 36 % was observed in Al-Ti-Zr-Nb-Ta refractory high entropy alloy having coherent BCC/B2 structure prepared via L-DED from pre-alloyed powders [30]. The smaller ductility of 8 % attained in the 3D printed Cr₁₅Nb₂₈Ti₂₃Zr₃₄ alloy can be partly attributed to the presence of the brittle Laves phase particles homogeneously distributed in the matrix and also to the contamination of material by oxygen during the long-term

homogenization treatment, when oxygen content increased to about 0.6 wt% (3.0 at%). The influence of the oxygen content on the mechanical properties of Ti₄₀Zr₂₅Nb₂₅Ta₁₀ high entropy alloy prepared by arc melting was investigated in [31]. Increasing oxygen content from 0.5 at% to 2.0 at% was found to increase the tensile strength at a rate of about 180 MPa/1.0 at% O, but tensile ductility rapidly decreased from about 12 % (0.5 at% O) to 2 % (2 at% O).

The serrated flow observed on the deformation curves at 400 °C (cf. Fig. 12a) can be attributed to the Portevin–Le Chatelier (PLC) effect. The presence of the PLC effect was observed also in the equiatomic HfNbTaTi refractory high entropy alloy of bcc structure and CoCrFeMnNi high entropy alloy with fcc structure prepared by arc melting and deformed in tension at 400 °C [32,33]. The mechanism of the PLC effect in the HEA is not fully understood. Tsai et al. [33] proposed the explanation of the PLC in fcc HEA based on the in-situ rearrangement of substitutional solute atoms by “local dislocation-core diffusion”. The solute atoms adjacent to the dislocation line reduce the strain energy by adjusting their relative positions. The solutes with larger atomic radii tend to gather at tensile strain sources, while solutes with smaller atomic radii are prone to cluster at compressive strain sources. This adjustment can reduce the overall strain energy, thereby pinning the dislocation. As a result, an increased value of stress is required to depin the dislocations from the solute atom atmosphere.

5. Conclusions

Refractory Cr₁₅Nb₂₈Ti₂₃Zr₃₄ complex concentrated alloy was successfully prepared from the blend of elemental powders by laser directed energy deposition technique. It was found that the laser power and the temperature of the substrate plate significantly affect the homogeneity of deposited samples. Both, the number of unmelted Nb particles and cracks decreases with increasing laser power and substrate plate temperature. Insulated ceramic fibre plate was used to increase the overall substrate plate temperature by laser-induced preheating. Temperature of the insulated substrate plate during deposition was by 200 °C higher as compared to the conventional conductive substrate plate. Laser power of 500 W, substrate plate temperature of 500 °C and printing speed of 850 mm/min are suitable deposition parameters for the preparation of crack free material with very low porosity. The resulting chemical composition of the deposited samples was affected by the Cr evaporation. Cr content was found to increase along the direction of specimen deposition. Homogenization heat treatment at 1200 °C resulted in the dissolution of residual unmelted Nb particles present in the as-deposited state. Locally homogeneous material consisting of bcc matrix and fine Cr₂(Zr, Nb, Ti) Laves phase particles was obtained after homogenization treatment. The content of the Laves phase increases along the deposition direction due to the increased Cr content. Homogenized alloy exhibits the exceptionally high yield stress of 1558 MPa and the elongation to fracture about 8 % at RT. The yield stress decreased only by 20 % at the temperature of 400 °C, while the ductility of 8 % remains unchanged. By utilizing suitable deposition conditions and parameters, L-DED is capable of producing complex concentrated alloys on the basis of refractory elemental powders with high melting temperatures.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomáš Krajnák: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Dalibor Preisler:** Visualization, Investigation. **Mariano Casas-Luna:** Visualization. **Miloš Janeček:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Jan Džugan:** Writing – review & editing. **Jan Kout:** Investigation. **Josef Stráský:** Writing – review & editing. **Jiří Kozlík:** Validation, Methodology. **Petr Harcuba:** Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15424511> under the CC-BY 4.0 license.

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